
DEVELOPMENT OF MONITORING INSTRUMENTS OF EFFICIENCY OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7881932>

Khamrakulov Ikhtiyor Bakhtiyorovich

Researcher, Fergana polytechnic institute

Annotation.

one of the areas of effective industrial development in our Republic is small industrial zones. The small industrial zones is being created on the basis of unused areas of state-owned facilities, operating at a loss, unused areas of economically disadvantaged and low-income enterprises. Small industrial zones are instrumental in bringing the Real support and development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship by the state to a new high level.

Keywords.

small industrial zone, network, industry, production, social efficiency.

The composition of small industrial zones includes participants engaged in various types of activities in the field of industries. This, in turn, leads to the fact that the production composition of small industrial zones is different. Therefore, the need arises to assess the indicators of financial and economic social efficiency of projects that are part of small industrial zones, while at the same time assessing the indicators of efficiency of small industrial zones. These indicators are also important in assessing the state of SIZ and their comparative assessment. Another important aspect of these indicators is that they serve as an information base in determining measures for the state regulation and support of SIZ.

The criteria for the effectiveness of siz include:

- * territorial effect from the construction of small industrial zones (increase in the volume of regional production);
 - social efficiency (employment of the population, income support);
 - financial (receipts to the state, local budget, payments to various funds);
 - environmental efficiency (environmental impact of the activities of small industrial zones).

- * influence on the development of production and service enterprises based on the establishment of cooperative relations with enterprises of the territory.

One of the important mechanisms for solving problems related to the development of small and medium-sized entrepreneurship, employment of the population and technological development of industry in developed foreign countries is industrial parks, technopolises and industrial zones. Currently, there are 400 industrial parks operating in the United States and China, 200 in Germany, 262 in Turkey, and about 200 in Vietnam. These zones are playing a fundamental role in the formation of a modern technological base of production, the introduction of innovations in production, and the creation and maintenance of products with a high capacity of science.

Particular attention is paid to the scientific study of the issues of developing industrial parks, technopolises and industrial zones in less developed and economically undeveloped areas in world countries, improving the efficiency of economic potential and resource use, deepening industrial cooperation between large and small production enterprises, increasing investment attractiveness in areas with small industrial zones, on this basis, competitive production and population employment. Also, the problems of innovation in the construction of small industrial zones, the development of conceptual models that fully cover the principles and trends of modern, the use of these as an important lever of the state economic are considered from the areas of scientific research in this regard.

Special attention is paid to the establishment and development of small industrial zones, which make an important contribution to the acceleration of industrial development in Uzbekistan. In particular, the tasks of "modernization and diversification of the leading sectors of the national economy of the country, deep processing of local raw materials resources, further development of high-tech Processing Networks, localization of production, achieving deep structural changes in industry, effective use of the existing industrial potential of regions" are defined in this regard. Currently, efforts are being made to achieve a synergistic effect as a result of the implementation of the state's industrial, the social and economic development of the regions where small industrial zones are located, the involvement of unused raw materials in the regions, the production of Labor and financial resources in the strengthening of cooperative relations between enterprises.

Industrial Park is understood as a godly structural element of the economy, which is provided by the company of the head of Service and efficient development, whose activities are guaranteed by the state and have the opportunity to receive benefits under the unified development concept and

infrastructure of the Development Complex. The main basic elements of the Industrial park are the presence of a plot of land destined for industrial development, the presence of a Bashkir company and infrastructure (autonomy, transport, Finance and social), special economic conditions, a unified development concept, the availability of resources and opportunities for departure to the sales markets.

The owners of the property participating in the development of the industrial zone will be determined on the basis of the contract and according to the choice.

In its work on the issues of building and investing industrial zones in the structure of the municipal structure, the definition of the industrial zone is given as follows: the industrial zone is an area of land, which is a municipal property, approved by the supreme body, according to the basic construction plan, for the organization of production, allocated by the municipality to industrial construction. In municipal structures, the industrial zone is formed as follows: the administrative body of the municipal structure copies the allocation of land area for the construction of production and infrastructure facilities from the upper administrative body (city, province). If the answer is positive, this land area will be allocated for an industrial area, a niche will be developed in the zone for production and the construction of Bashkir social facilities, the main construction plan will be approved. Then the land is allocated and construction is carried out according to the main plan. Here, industrial production, infrastructure and the sanitary zone are located in proportion.

The study of the experience of the construction and development of industrial zones in the Chinese Republic of Halk evokes great heat. Two factors contribute to the sustainable development of industrial zones. The first factor is the comprehensive use of the energy of private entrepreneurs. The second is the effect (the effect of synergy), which arises from the activity of the industrial zone as a single system, based on a private economy. Industrial zones are important in the economic development of Chinese territories.

Today, there are more than three hundred industrial zones in the province of Zhejiang. This stream is produced in an industrial zone of industrial production of cash in an average of 100 million rubles per year. yuan. In general, industrial zones based on private entrepreneurship are hit as the main force that undermines the development of the economy of mintakas.

Industrial zones are not large firms, mainly small and urticate enterprises. They can be curled up as tsexes. Tsex are driven by different types of processing

activities. If certain cexs develop certain component kism or intermediate products, then the heads will produce the final product. The kuplab small tsexs located in the single khududd form a single industrial development complex, and such a complex is capable of developing a wide range of goods for the national and Jaxon markets. The pillar of the industrial zone is made up of private firms that develop final products and services in the number of Kup, and this includes the following: private business, enterprises based on share capital, firms with external trade, enterprises with Kushma. The industrial zone includes ham: enterprises providing primary products, components, CISM and equipment; enterprises dealing with retail and wholesale trade, intermediary enterprises in export and import Sox, financial and information service providers; qualified personnel training agencies, standards development organizations, research and experienced design.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Ихтиёр Бахтиёрович Хамрақулов (2021). КИЧИК САНОАТ ЗОНАЛАРИНИ БАРПО ЭТИШ ВА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. *Scientific progress*, 2 (7), 586-592.
2. Ихтиёр Бахтиёрович Хамрақулов (2022). КИЧИК САНОАТ ЗОНАЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ МОҲИЯТИ ВА ЎЗИГА ХОС ҲУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *Scientific progress*, 3 (1), 328-334.
3. Хамрақулов Ихтиёр Бахтиёрович (2022). КИЧИК САНОАТ ЗОНАЛАРИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОН ФАОЛЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШНИНГ СТРАТЕГИК ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2 (Special Issue 2), 140-146.
4. Хамрақулов, И. Б. (2021). Теоретические основы создания и развития малых промышленных зон. In *НАУКА СЕГОДНЯ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ* (pp. 49-51).
5. Khamrakulov, I. (2022). Organizational and economic foundations for creating small industrial zones in Uzbekistan. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 11(10), 233-237.
6. Asqarova, A., Xonkeldiyeva, K., Abdumutalibova, X., & Murotova, D. (2021). Issues of increasing the competitiveness of light industry enterprises. In *Наука сегодня: проблемы и пути решения* (pp. 48-49).

7. Хайдаров, Х., Нурматова, И., & Хонкелдиева, К. (2021). Факторы формирования сильного конкурентного рынка в текстильной промышленности. In НАУКА СЕГОДНЯ: ВЫЗОВЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ (pp. 59-61).
8. Asqarova, A. M., Xonkeldiyeva, K. R., Nomonjonova, F. U., Qodirova, S. Q., & Arabxonova, X. A. (2021). Classification Of Competition In The Market Of Light Industrial Goods And The Factors That Shape It. The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations, 3(01), 43-46.
9. Asqarova, A. M., Xonkeldiyeva, K. R., Abdugarimova, R. A., Xudoyberdiyeva, X. B., & Egamberdiyeva, N. B. (2021). Theories Of Marketing Strategies To Increase The Competitiveness Of Light Industry Enterprises. The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations, 3(01), 40-42.
10. Хонкелдиева, К., Рахимова, Х., & Хасанхужаева, У. (2021). Предупреждение преступности среди несовершеннолетних. In Наука сегодня: факты, тенденции, прогнозы (pp. 34-35).
11. Xonkeldiyeva, K., & Xo'jamberdiyev, J. (2020). Экономика и социум.
12. Xonkeldiyeva, K. R. (2021). Features of management of textile industry enterprises based on the cluster approach. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(9), 780-783.
13. Zokirova, S. X., Akbarov, R. F., Isagaliyeva, S. M., & Xonkeldiyeva, K. R. (2021). Sand Distribution In Central Fergana. The American journal of interdisciplinary innovations and research, 3(01), 113-117.
14. Zokirova, S. X., Ahmedova, D., Akbarov, R. F., & Xonkeldiyeva, K. R. (2021). Light Industry Enterprises In Marketing Activities Experience Of Foreign Countries In The Use Of Cluster Theory. The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations, 3(01), 36-39.
15. Xonkeldiyeva K., & Xo'Jamberdiyev J. (2020). IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS OF INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION. Экономика и социум, (3 (70)), 145-147.
16. Хонкелдиева, К., & Мўйдинжонова, М. (2020). Актуальные проблемы решения безработицы в Республике Узбекистан. In Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования (pp. 18-19).
17. Хонкелдиева, К., & Хўжамбердиев, Ж. (2020). Проблемы развития организации: управленческий и логистический аспекты. In Наука сегодня: история и современность (pp. 17-19).
18. Хонкелдиева, К., & Толибжонова, М. (2020). Механизм формирования инновационного процесса в текстильном производстве как

основа адаптации к процессам глобализации. In Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования (pp. 15-16).

19. Хонкелдиева, К., & Абдусатторова, З. (2020). Социальная инфраструктура как фактор социально-экономического развития региона. In Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования (pp. 17-18).

20. Хонкелдиева, К., & Фарохиддинова, З. (2020). Гендерное равенство как ценность права. Наука сегодня: факты, тенденции, прогнозы: материя.

21. Хонкелдиева, К., & Мўйдинжонова, М. (2020). Необходимые условия обеспечения гендерного равенства. In Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования (pp. 40-41).

22. Хонкелдиева, К., Рахимова, Х., & Абдусатторова, З. (2020). Проблемы развития социального обеспечения населения. In Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования (pp. 42-43).

23. Хонкелдиева, К. (2020). Актуальные вопросы повышения экономического потенциала текстильной промышленности. In Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования (pp. 13-15).

24. Хонкелдиева, К., & Фарохиддинова, З. (2020). Гендерное равенство как ценность права. In Наука сегодня: факты, тенденции, прогнозы (pp. 61-62).

25. Хонкелдиева, К., & Маматкулова, Ф. (2020). Социально-экономические аспекты устойчивого развития предприятия. In Наука сегодня: факты, тенденции, прогнозы (pp. 36-37).

26. Хонкелдиева, К., & Фарохиддинова, З. (2020). Оценка влияния рынка труда на уровень безработицы в республике Узбекистан. In Наука сегодня: факты, тенденции, прогнозы (pp. 37-38).